

8T – W Duality

To the Memory of Steven Weinberg

O Manor

September 6, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the second first term of the primordial coupling constants series, and in particular the numeric representation of the electron, and the Boson of the weak interaction it is possible to represent their duality. In addition, the author makes a prediction regarding the emission of the photon; in particular, the photon should be emitted from the W^- boson.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2. A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Let us analyze the first coupling term in the primorial:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + e^-] + W^-$$

The electron and the Boson of the weak interaction are represented by the same element, the majestic three is for the electron, and the three net variations are for the W^+ boson. The kernel is the three and the image is both the electron and the W^- Boson. Such a duality among those two is in agreement with modern particle physics that states that the electron and the W^- Bosons have the same charge. The same applies to the opposite charges. Because of the duality of those two.

Because there is no numerical difference, we can replace the order as mentioned in the 8T thesis, page seventy-eight.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + W^-] + e^-$$

We can also replace the actual elements:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + W^-] + W^-$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \longrightarrow [(8 * 3) + e^-] + e^-$$

The coupling term with two electrons as an example, could describe the motion of free electron that could join another atom, the electron tradeoff that ignite the entire chemistry. In addition, we can make a prediction regarding photon emission. In particular, the author predict that photon can be emitted from the Boson of the weak interaction. Therefore, in a way we have Bosons emitting Bosons. The emission is described by the third coupling term, given by the equivalence relation between the electron and W^- Boson, as a tribute to a recent giant of history, Weinberg, the following will be called the W Duality:

$$W^- \equiv (e^-)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \equiv [(24 * 5) + (W^-)] + \gamma$$

Since the coupling constants series is commutative, we can go further and make an additional prediction:

$$[(24 * 5) + (W^-)] + \gamma \longrightarrow [(24 * 5) + \gamma] + (W^-)$$

This prediction is breaking the rules of the primordial in which we regard the invariant three to be the destabilizer that lead to a net variation, but since the coupling magnitude is preserved, it is possible to change the order of the terms themselves. The order is a reflection on the element that is being propagated. So according to the last prediction, a (W^-) will be propagated from a photon, a massless particle. It is a wild prediction, but at the same time very interesting, maybe even correct as the photon as energy which could morph onto mass.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad